

B r i F a c e

H2020:MSCA-IF-2018

Novel assessment of bridge retrofitting measures through Interface Efficiency Indices (InterFeis) using a Guided Wave-based monitoring method

(H2020-MSCA-IF-2018 Marie Skłodowska-Curie)

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D3: Dissemination & Exploitation Plan (DEP)

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Objectives of the dissemination plan

Dissemination plan aims to present the strategy of disseminating project progress and results to the relevant scientific communities, stakeholders and general audiences, promote the benefits of adopting the Briface strategies and raise awareness at the engineering and policy-making level of its importance.

1. Promote resilience research by developing an innovative theoretical framework that fuses monitoring strategy in making new, existing or strengthened infrastructure resilient.
2. Promote material science in enhancing existing infrastructure assets
3. Produce new monitoring-based insights into managing of infrastructure for shifting transport networks towards resilience
4. Enhance multi-way engagement with stakeholders, industry policy makers to effectively transfer Briface outputs to further implement the world trends, awareness and strategies towards existing structures.

The main goal of communication and dissemination is to maximise opportunities to promote, communicate and disseminate research results throughout the lifetime of Briface, and beyond. This will ensure that key stakeholders can contribute to and assess on the use of the findings in a timely manner.

Dissemination, communication and exploitation activities of Briface pursue four main objectives, namely to:

1. raise interest and awareness around resilience practices in transport networks based on monitoring and enhanced strengthening measures
2. encourage citizens in Europe to actively provide feedback on infrastructure decisions to ensure that projects meet the needs of local communities and builds public trust according to the engagement of UK government in constructive dialogue
3. identify expectations among stakeholders and policy-makers
4. disseminate results in strategic and targeted ways.

A coherent, multi-layered strategy to effectively publish and exploit Briface findings will provide combined input from academy, industry, stakeholders and wide audiences throughout the entire duration of the project but also beyond its completion. Effective dissemination, communication and exploitation of findings are central to successful high-impact research, especially in the cases that the activities involve multiple groups of academic and non-academic partners and diverse audiences.

The aim of WP6 is to coordinate communication activities with all work packages. Its main aims are:

1. to build a community around the project including all relevant stakeholders, ensuring long-term impact and use of outcomes/results/strategies
2. establish an easily recognisable project identity
3. raise awareness of Briface at national and international levels.

WP6 will use a variety of communication channels and tools to:

1. disseminate the results and outcomes of the Briface project
2. effectively communicate throughout the project to involve and actively engage relevant stakeholders as necessary
3. facilitate the full exploitation of results and outcomes by diverse groups and audiences.

Table 1 contains all the methods to be used and the planned activities as well as the targeted group (see Table 2) and the key performance indicator that measures effectiveness of the method used.

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Table 1: Methods for disseminating results and communication activities

Methods	Activities	Time of submission/completion	Target group	Aim	Key Performance Indicator-KPI (number)
Papers	Publications	J1: 3/2020, J2: 05/2021	Scientists/ scientific community Stakeholders Investors Customers Policy makers Civil Society	Promotion Innovation Open access	Citations Collaborations Fund raising Applications Guidelines
Conferences	Publications Participation	(publications) C1: 7/2020, C2: 5/2021 C3: 12/2021 (participation) 09/2019	Scientists/ scientific community Stakeholders Investors Customers Policy makers Civil Society	Promotion	Citations Collaborations Fund raising Applications Guidelines Networking
Talks in Surrey (open days, Festival of Research)	Presentation	10/2021	Scientists/ scientific community	Promotion Raising awareness	Attendees
Talks to public audiences	Presentations	4/2021	Diverse audiences School students Diverse audiences	Promotion Raising awareness	Attendees
Talks & meetings with stakeholders	Presentations	2020-21	Scientists/ scientific community Stakeholders Investors Customers Policy makers Civil Society	Promotion Engagement Raising awareness	Attendees Collaborations Fund raising
Social media posts	Information release on progress/results	2020-2021	Scientists/ scientific community Stakeholders Investors Customers Policy makers Civil Society	Promotion Raising awareness	Visits Likes
Multimedia releases	Information release on progress/results	2020-2021	Scientists/ scientific community Stakeholders Investors Customers Policy makers Civil Society	Promotion Raising awareness	Visits
Press releases	Information release on progress/results/ new collaborations	2020-2021	Diverse audiences	Promotion Engagement Raising awareness	Visits

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Website	Information release on progress/results/new collaborations	2020-2021	Scientists/ scientific community Stakeholders Investors Customers Policy makers Civil Society	Promotion Engagement Raising awareness	Visits Traffic
e-Newsletter	Information release on progress/results/new collaborations	2020-2021	Scientists/ scientific community Stakeholders Investors Customers Policy makers Civil Society Diverse audiences	Promotion Engagement Raising awareness	Visits Traffic
Participation to workshops	Participation Networking	3/2021	Scientists/ scientific community Stakeholders Investors Customers Policy makers Civil Society	Promotion Engagement Raising awareness	Collaborations
Flyer	Information release on progress/results/new collaborations	2020-2021	Scientists/ scientific community Stakeholders Investors Customers Policy makers Civil Society Diverse audiences	Promotion Engagement Raising awareness	Addresses
Logo	Design Publish	09/2019	Diverse audiences	Recognise project's identity	Future tags
Organisation of workshops	Seminar Presentation Discussions Brain storming	3/2021	Scientists/ scientific community Stakeholders Investors Customers Policy makers Civil Society	Promotion Engagement Raising awareness	Attendees Collaborations
Brokerage event	Presentation Discussions Brain storming	4/2021	Scientists/ scientific community Stakeholders Investors Customers Policy makers Civil Society	Promotion Engagement Raising awareness	Collaborations
TEDX talks	Presentation Discussions	2021	Diverse audiences General public	Engagement Raising awareness	Attendees

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Thematic events	Presentation Discussions	2021	Diverse audiences	Engagement Raising awareness	Attendees
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Table 2: Audiences and evaluating criteria/method

Audiences	Number of persons/groups	Evaluation criteria/method
Scientists/ scientific community	15/4	citations/collaborations
Stakeholders	26	collaborations
Investors	1	fund-raising
Customers	1	fund-raising/ applications
Policy makers	1	technical guidelines
Civil Society	-	incorporation in international regulations
University students	-	questionnaire
Diverse audiences	40	questionnaire
School	-	questionnaire